

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	4
2. The role of the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)	5
3. The EEAB selection process	6
3.1 Identifying potential Experts	6
3.2 Contacting the Experts	6
3.3 The Experts' agreement	7
4. Members of the EEAB	8
5. Meeting Overview	10
5.1 Interview with Mr. Socratis Socratous.....	10
5.2 Interview with Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis.....	11
5.3 Interview with Dr. (Mr.) Nektarios Chrysoulakis.....	12
5.4 Interview with Mr. Peter Fane.....	12
6. Results and recommendations	14
7. List of members of EEAB	15
ANNEX I	16

1. Executive Summary

This document aims to provide an overview of the most important points discussed during the 1st External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) meeting of the RECAP project (experts' recommendations, partners' comments, important issues raised, etc.).

Regarding the structure of the current document, Chapter 2 presents an overview of the role of the EEAB in the project, while Chapter 3 describes the methodology for the selection process for the EEAB members for the first phase of the project. The members of the current EEAB are presented in Chapter 4 with brief descriptions of their expertise. Detailed minutes of the meetings held during this period (month 3 to month 5 of the project) are presented in Chapter 5. Finally, the document concludes with an analysis of the recommendations of the members to the RECAP project which are summarised in Chapter 6.

2. The role of the External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)

RECAP (Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP) is an Innovation Action project to the topic INSO-1-2015: ICT-enabled open government: Pilots on personalised and mobile public services and/ or pilots on transparency. The inclusion of an EEAB to the RECAP project is considered as an important matter for the success of the project and hence it has been initiated from the early stages of the project and will be a constant procedure.

The EEAB is a counselling body providing advice and guidance for the development of the project to ensure its high quality and excellence. It will serve as an external body providing the project team with independent scrutiny on the project's development and enhance the dissemination potential of the project. They are a valued group of experts who will meet regularly with the project consortium throughout the project duration.

3. The EEAB selection process

3.1 Identifying potential Experts

For the first phase of selection of the EEAB members, an open and transparent process has been followed. All partners have taken part in the procedure and it was done through personal contacts. The aim was to establish an initial list of experts to be approved by the Consortium.

All partners were asked to identify experts from agricultural spectrum, as well as from different types of organisations, such as consultant companies, farmer associations, public institutions and companies related to Satellite Remote Sensing. For this purpose a template Invitation Letter (**ANNEX I**) for the EEAB members was prepared and an excel file was created in order to record specific information.

Requirements for the agricultural experts of the EAB include:

- proven expertise in the agricultural field;
- at least 5 years of professional academic/ business/ policy experience;
- publications in the respective field, such as reports, working papers, publication in journals and/ or policy documents of the EU institutions and relevant international organisations;
- good knowledge of the EU research and innovation policy and Horizon 2020 will be considered an advantage;
- good communication in written and spoken English;
- readiness to travel.

Ideally the members of the EEAB shall not only be experts in their field, but also have formal or informal influence within the respective networks.

3.2 Contacting the Experts

In order to establish a long- term and dedicated EEAB, all partners should pay special attention to a good geographical coverage of EU countries and to a world-wide reputation of the EEAB members in the scientific and technical fields addressed by the project.

4 experts were invited to form part of the EEAB via email Invitation Letter. If some of these 4 invited experts declined the invitation to join the EEAB a further selection of experts would be carried out until an EEAB of 4 was composed. The next step was to contact these experts and to propose them to participate in the EEAB via conference call outlining the main activities of RECAP and the tasks of the EEAB, the expected contribution and the reimbursement offered to the experts.

The mandate of the EEAB is to provoke and contribute to in-depth discussions on key issues of relevance to the RECAP project, with a focus on earth observation and agriculture.

The EEAB role is expected to be performed along the entire project duration (30 months) and further experts would be added during the course of the project. The work of the EEAB is related to the Task 1.2: External Expert Advisory Board Management, part of the WP1- Project Management.

When it is essential for the implementation of the project an advisory board teleconference will be held to review progress, address strategic questions and plan for the coming period. The EEAB may also hold one or more additional conference calls at other times of the year as particular issues develop. EEAB members are expected to join at least one of these calls per year. The Coordinator will provide to the EEAB members a schedule with relevant project meetings and events. The timing of the other meeting will be agreed between

the RECAP partners in collaboration with the EEAB. The decisions about which EEAB members will participate at which RECAP meetings, will be made during the first meeting of the Advisory Board.

EEAB members' responsibilities include:

- participate in at least one conference call per year, as requested;
- provide ad-hoc feedback when requested by the project Coordinator or the project officer;
- provide written feedback and advice to RECAP partners on the quality of the results achieved throughout the implementation of RECAP project;
- advise on the contribution of RECAP to the EU research policy, as well as to other policies of relevance, including those related to earth observation and agriculture;
- review of project deliverables and identify strengths and weaknesses with respect to the objectives of the project and the intended impact, and to provide written feedback.

After each meeting, DRAXIS will prepare a report all summarising conclusions, observations on project results and recommendations on actions for impact creation. DRAXIS will ensure that the conclusions and recommendations of the EEAB are adequately taken into consideration by the Executive Board in the decision making process during the project.

There is a limited budget allocated to cover EEAB travel expenses (flight and accommodation). Due to this limited amount, the consortium will decide how to distribute this budget among the EEAB members. **The consortium** can also decide to make any meeting or interview by video conference.

All communication between RECAP and the EEAB will be held in English as lingua franca. EEAB members are encouraged to communicate in a clear way, and to ask for clarification whenever necessary. Members commit to respond to correspondence within a reasonable time period. Correspondence will normally be sent by email. Members will ordinarily have two weeks to provide feedback on documents sent for consultation. The coordinator may shorten this period in some instances to keep project deadlines.

The activities held in conjunction with the EEAB and their outcomes will be reported in the public deliverables D1.2, D1.7, D1.8 and D1.9 due in M4, M14, M23 and M30 of the project.

3.3 The Experts' agreement

The EEAB consists of 4 Experts and all the parties have signed the EEAB non-disclosure agreement that outlines the main activities of RECAP project and the tasks of the EEAB, the expected contribution and the reimbursement offered to the experts.

4. Members of the EEAB

The creation of the EEAB is a crucial procedure for the highly quality and excellence of the project. The EEAB consists of 4 members. A short description of the qualifications of the members of the RECAP EEAB is presented below:

Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis

Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis is Senior Policy Advisor on policies related to agri-food cooperatives and Producer Organisations. Mr. Kalaitzis is of Greek Nationality, and a business economist with post graduate studies on agricultural economics. He has worked for more than a decade as a researcher on agricultural cooperatives at the Netherlands Institute for Cooperative Entrepreneurship and at Wageningen University in the Netherlands on agri-food marketing and food supply chains. Since 2008 and until the fall of 2016, he has lobbied in Brussels for Copa-Cogeca the European Farmers and European Agri-Cooperatives organisation, as a cooperative expert and policy adviser on agri-cooperatives, internal market and EU Budget.

Mr. Peter Fane

Principal consultant Mr. Peter Fane has been advising farmers, trade bodies and agribusiness professionals on all aspects of European policy for over 20 years. He is a surveyor and agricultural consultants with extensive practical experience of agriculture and estate management. Prior to establishing Eurinco, Mr. Fane was Director of the British Agricultural Bureau, the Brussels office of the UK Farmers' unions and farm cooperatives in the 1990s. Mr. Fane has worked as a surveyor in both private and public sectors, and is a former Director of the RICS Land Group, where he was responsible for rural, environmental and other professional groups. He is retained to advise the RICS on public policy issues, and is the principal author of the "Rural Vision for CAP". He was a board member of the Government's former Countryside Agency. He chaired the Agency's Landscape, Access and Recreation division and was Deputy Chair of the Agency at the time of its abolition in 2006.

Dr. (Mr.) Nektarios Chrysoulakis

Dr. Nektarios Chrysoulakis is a Director of Research, at the Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas (FORTH) in Heraklion, Greece. He holds a BSc in Physics, a MSc in Environmental Physics and PhD in Remote Sensing from the University of Athens. He has been involved in R&D projects funded from organisations such as the European Union, the European Space Agency and the Ministries of Environment, Development, Culture and Education. He has considerable experience in the area of Earth Observation and GIS. His main research interests include urban research, urban energy balance, natural and technological risk analysis, thermal infrared imagery and surface temperature studies, environmental monitoring and change detection. He is the coordinator of the H2020 (Space) project URBANFLUXES (<http://urbanfluxes.eu>). Dr. Chrysoulakis was also the Coordinator of the FP7 projects BRIDGE (<http://www.bridge-fp7.eu>) and GEOURBAN (<http://geourban-fp7-eranet.com>). He also participates in the H2020 (Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials) project ECOPOTENTIAL (Improving future Ecosystem benefits through Earth Observations). He has more than 150 publications in peer-review journals and conference proceedings.

Mr. Socrates Socratous

Mr. Socrates Socratous is Senior Officer at the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organization with more than 10 years of experience in Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Implementation aspects. Mr. Socratous is an IT expert with strong Management experience accompanied by relevant academic education. He is a holder of engineering (Electrical and Informatics Engineering) diploma and two Masters Degrees in Management Information Systems and in Management Business Administration. For the last 10 years he

is working at the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organization and he has a great involvement in the design, reengineering, build and implementation of the IACS (Integrated Administration and Control System) system that the organization uses. Moreover he is fully familiar with the CAP regulation and implementing acts as well as of the working documents issued by the Dg-Agri towards implementing the CAP.

5. Meeting Overview

The scope of the External Expert Advisory Board meetings was to inform EEAB members about RECAP and the challenges the consortium faces, and to offer the RECAP consortium the chance to elicit some initial crucial recommendations for the project's implementation. The meetings were held via an online collaboration tool. Several interesting and useful recommendations were provided by the EEAB members.

5.1 Interview with Mr. Socrates Socratous

The online meeting with Mr. Socrates Socratous was held on 29th of July 2016 via skype. Participants of the online meeting were Ms. Ifigeneia- Maria Tsioutsia from DRAXIS and Mr. Socrates Socratous and it lasted for approximately 30 minutes. At first, Ms. Tsioutsia welcomed Mr. Socratous and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Then, Mr. Socratous presented himself. Ms. Tsioutsia briefly presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Furthermore, she presented the problem, the objectives of the RECAP project, the main components of the envisioned platform and the most critical indicators that will be used to assess the impact of the project. The topics discussed are presented below:

How familiar are the public authorities with the existing online cross – compliance tools?

Due to his position in the Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation, Mr. Socratous pointed that unfortunately the public authorities are not familiar with the existing online cross-compliance tools. They used to monitor the cross-compliance procedure only through traditional tools such as GPS.

How do public authorities react with new monitoring practices? How should RECAP approach them?

Mr. Socratous said that the majority of public authorities are always reluctant to adopt new monitoring practices and it requires a lot of effort to persuade them into utilising new techniques. Mr. Socratous suggested that RECAP should be introduced to public authorities from the beginning of the RECAP implementation. Moreover, Mr. Socratous claimed that there are many opportunities for new innovative solutions in the agricultural sector and that Cypriot public authorities will welcome the RECAP solution. Finally, he mentioned that such a tool will be useful in universities for research purposes.

What are the potential barriers to the use of RECAP platform?

Based on his experience, Mr. Socratous mentioned that there are many barriers that will deter public authorities from using the RECAP platform. Firstly, there is lack of technological resources that could support such a tool. Secondly, the personnel is not familiar with technical knowledge of advanced tools so as to exploit the full benefits of the platform, and that is due to their limited experience and their age. Lastly, the RECAP platform should be designed as a tool which will provide information based on a business model focused on specific critical points increasing the business value of the platform.

How can we build capacity and educate the public authorities to monitor farmers' compliance to standards through the RECAP platform?

Mr. Socratous mentioned that consultation on public authorities should be made from the early stages of the project by providing them with appropriate knowledge and tips. He also said that awareness building is important. The arising challenge is their level of readiness to welcome participation approaches in general. Moreover, he mentioned that the platform should be updated in a regular basis and training courses should be conducted in technical issues.

- 🌱 *What strategies do you believe that RECAP should develop in order to disseminate the results and services and create awareness among public authorities?*

Mr. Socratous pointed that the main purpose of the dissemination activities are to raise awareness and engage as many users as possible from the early stages of the RECAP project. Mr. Socratous suggested that many awareness raising campaigns on sustainability issues should be organised aiming to receive feedback from engaged people.

5.2 Interview with Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis

The online meeting with Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis was held on 24th of August 2016 via skype. Participants of the online meeting were Ms. Ifigeneia- Maria Tsioutsia and Mrs. Machi Simeonidou from DRAXIS and Mr. Prodromos Kalaitzis and it lasted for approximately 1 hour. At first, Mrs. Simeonidou welcomed Mr. Kalaitzis and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Then, Mr. Kalaitzis presented himself. Ms. Tsioutsia briefly presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Furthermore, she presented the problem, the objectives of the RECAP project, the main components of the envisioned platform and the most critical indicators that will be used to assess the impact of the project. The topics discussed are presented below:

- 🌱 *How familiar are the consultants with the existing online cross-compliance self-assessment tools?*

Mr. Kalaitzis mentioned that the majority of agricultural consultants who specialised in providing services on the cross-compliance procedure are quite familiar with the existing online cross-compliance self-assessment tools. Mr. Kalaitzis also pointed that the consultants pay special attention to the reliability of the measures, criteria and details that are provided by such tools.

- 🌱 *What are the main issues that farmers face dealing with the cross-compliance standards? What are the services that the consultant provides more frequently?*

Mr. Kalaitzis said that the inferiority of farmers are willing to use online self-assessment tools because the majority of them have limited technological knowledge. Mr. Kalaitzis also mentioned that many of them face difficulties in proving the validity of their declared land despite the fact that the information is collected from the cadastre. Moreover, he indicated that the most common services that the consultants provide are the finance and accounting related to the farmer's land management.

- 🌱 *Do you believe that the farmers will be willing to share their information with the consultants?*

Mr. Kalaitzis referred to the privacy issues raised by the farmers' unwillingness to share their information publicly. He pointed that authorized representatives from relevant public authorities, organisations or unions should earnestly support the RECAP platform and abet farmers to share their information without hesitation.

- 🌱 *What are the potential barriers to the use of RECAP platform?*

Mr. Kalaitzis mentioned that the main barrier to the use of RECAP platform is the unwillingness of the majority of the potential users. He strongly believes that this is a consequence of the users' lack of technical knowledge and motivation. He pointed that the RECAP consortium and the stakeholders should try to develop an early communication strategy plan based on users' needs and demands.

- 🌍 *What strategies do you believe that RECAP should develop in order to disseminate the results and services and create awareness among agricultural consultants?*

Mr. Kalaitzis suggested that the RECAP dissemination should start only after the platform is a well prepared product so that RECAP can build trust with users and convince them to use it.

5.3 Interview with Dr. (Mr.) Nektarios Chrysoulakis

The online meeting with Dr. (Mr.) Nektarios Chrysoulakis was held on 7th of September 2016 via skype. Participants of the online meeting were Ms. Ifigeneia- Maria Tsioutsia and Mr. Stelios Kotsopoulos from DRAXIS and Dr. Nektarios Chrysoulakis and it lasted for approximately 40 minutes. At first, Ms. Tsioutsia welcomed Dr. Chrysoulakis and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Then, Dr. Chrysoulakis presented himself. Ms. Tsioutsia briefly presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Furthermore, she presented the problem, the objectives of the RECAP project, the main components of the envisioned platform and the most critical indicators that will be used to assess the impact of the project. The topics discussed are presented below:

- 🌍 *Do you believe that the Earth Observation data is applicable to the RECAP project?*

Dr. Chrysoulakis mentioned that as far as he knows, the use of Earth Observation (EO) data and in general the satellite remote sensing technologies have already been applicable in similar applications in agriculture. However, he pointed that despite the wide acceptance of these technologies in the agricultural sector and in other sectors too, the satellite remote sensing is not always the solution to every problem. Dr. Chrysoulakis said that there might be several constraints on the applicability of EO methods due to the spatial resolution of EO data, the crop type, the features of the object that are analysed or on the topography in which the remote sensing is applied. Finally, he expressed his certainty, that the combined use of the very high resolution data that OPEKEPE receives through the DGAGRI of JRC with the SENTINEL 2 multispectral data, some checkpoints of the cross-compliance list will be checked through the use of satellite remote sensing, supporting the in-fields inspections procedures.

- 🌍 *In what ways would the pilot cases have more effective results?*

Dr. Chrysoulakis suggested that pilot cases should be focused on one specific area since a pilot demonstrating project has many difficulties to be applied in the entire country. Moreover, he mentioned that the proper pilot operational environments should be established based on the cross-compliance checkpoints that would be specified.

5.4 Interview with Mr. Peter Fane

The online meeting with Mr. Peter Fane was held on 9th of September 2016 via skype. Participants of the online meeting were Ms. Ifigeneia- Maria Tsioutsia and Mr. Stelios Kotsopoulos from DRAXIS, Mr. Jason Beedell from Strutt & Parker and Mr. Peter Fane and it lasted for approximately 40 minutes. At first, Ms. Tsioutsia welcomed Mr. Fane and thanked him for his participation on the EEAB. Then, Mr. Fane presented himself. Ms. Tsioutsia briefly presented the project highlighting the key points of its future implementation. Furthermore, she presented the problem, the objectives of the RECAP project, the main components of the envisioned platform and the most critical indicators that will be used to assess the impact of the project. The topics discussed are presented below:

 Do you believe that the RECAP platform will be a useful tool for the consultants?

Mr. Fane pointed that there is a lot of information around regarding the cross-compliance and that the majority of the consultants are not looking for new information in new systems. They are just hoping to make their existing systems working better. He also mentioned that if RECAP platform is able to be integrated to their existing software, many of the consultants would be willing to use it.

 What are the potential barriers to the use of RECAP platform?

Mr. Fane said that most consultants are quite familiar with the cross-compliance meaning and the current paying system. As a result, they would be reluctant to change from a system that they are familiar with if it is not for a better way of working. He pointed that RECAP should offer them very special and specific services or tools in terms of improved access to the paying system.

 What do you believe RECAP should do in order to engage consultants?

Regarding UK, Mr. Fane mentioned that both farmers and consultants are aware that in the next few years there will be a completely different system in agricultural policy. He suggested that the RECAP platform should be developed in terms of other paying systems' simplicity and become a demonstrative tool of agricultural policy from which lessons would be learnt and help the public administrations to the adjustment process.

 What are the main issues that farmers face dealing with the cross-compliance standards?

Mr. Fane pointed that accuracy and complexity of the cross-compliance standards are the main issues that farmers have to deal with. There are number of regulations that farmers have to be familiar and comply with in order to avoid an eminent penalty.

6. Results and recommendations

Name	Recommendations and Suggestions	RECAP Actions	
		WP	Deliverables
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should take into consideration the possible reluctance of the public authorities to use the RECAP platform in the design of the RECAP platform.	WP2	D2.2
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should take into account to develop a user-friendly environment in the design of the RECAP platform due to the lack of technological resources and personnel's technical knowledge in advanced tools.	WP3	D3.1
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should pilot test the platform in contact with the public authorities.	WP4	D4.1, D4.2
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should try to build trust between the platform and the public authorities during the planning procedure and ensure that every information will be exploited in order to build awareness as soon as possible.	WP4, WP5	D4.1, D5.4, D5.5
Socrates Socratous	RECAP should pay more attention to the requirements and development of the platform regarding the public authorities in order to enable them to gain experience and set structure and the procedures that should be followed in the future.	WP2, WP4,	D2.2, D4.1, D5.5
Prodromos Kalaitzis	From the early stages of the project, RECAP should be in constant contact with representatives from public authorities, local organisations and unions and try to build trust between the platform and the farmers during either the dissemination or pilot planning procedure.	WP4, WP5	D4.1, D5.4, D5.5
Prodromos Kalaitzis	RECAP dissemination should start only after the platform is a well prepared product so that RECAP can build trust with users and convince them to use it.	WP5	D5.2, D5.5
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	RECAP should consider the constraints on the applicability of EO methods due to the spatial resolution of EO data, the crop type, the features of the object that are analysed or on the topography in which the remote sensing is applied.	WP3	D3.2
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	Pilot cases should be focused on one specific area and be established based on the cross-compliance checkpoints that would be specified.	WP4	D4.1
Peter Fane	RECAP platform should be integrated to the existing systems of the five pilot countries.	WP3	D3.1, D3.3
Peter Fane	RECAP platform should be a useful tool for the UK adjustment process in the new agricultural policy	-	-

7. List of members of EEAB

Name	Organisation & expertise
Prodromos Kalaitzis	Senior Policy Advisor, Cooperative enterprise policy and legislation
Peter Fane	Eurinco, European policy consultants, Agriculture, Rural development and renewable energy
Socrates Socratous	Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation
Nektarios Chrysoulakis	FORTH, Foundation for Research and Technology- Hellas

ANNEX I

Invitation to participate in the RECAP project External Expert Advisory Board

Dear ...,

We would like to invite you to become a distinguished member of the External Expert Advisory Board of the RECAP project. RECAP has received funding from the EC under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, which is the financial instrument of the EC that will offer funding to research projects for 7 years (2014 to 2020).

The project RECAP (*Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP*) aims to develop and pilot test a platform for the delivery of public services that will enable the improved implementation of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). RECAP proposes a methodology for improving the efficiency and transparency of the compliance monitoring procedure through a cloud-based Software as a Service (SaaS) platform which will make use of large volumes of publicly available data provided by satellite remote sensing, and user generated data.

The role of the members of the RECAP External Expert Advisory Board is to participate in project's meetings, in which they will review the project activities and outcomes, identify the strong/weak points with respect to the objectives of the project and the applications of the results, and provide expert recommendations. All travel and accommodation costs will be covered by the project budget.

The RECAP External Expert Advisory Board will be convened some times throughout the duration of the project either in meetings or in conference calls. With your collaboration we will be able to issue recommendations that will ensure the fulfillment of the project's objectives.

We are looking forward to welcoming you as a member of this unique group.

Do not hesitate to contact us for any further information or clarification.

Best regards,

Machi Simeonidou
RECAP Project Coordinator
DRAXIS Environmental S.A.